

The Role of Women Swachhagrahis in Sanitation Revolution and Women Empowerment: An Empirical Study of Ajmer District of Rajasthan

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Abstract

Lack of proper and safe sanitation facilities have lot of ill effects related to health, wellbeing, safety and environment. The ill effects are even more pronounced when it comes to women and girls as lack of sanitation not only affects their health but have direct bearing on their sense of safety, dignity and privacy. The Swachh Bharat Mission- Gramin was launched in 2014 with aim of making India open defecation free by 2nd October 2019, marking the 150th birth anniversary of Mahatma Gandhi. The mission not only aimed to end open defecation through building toilet infrastructure but sustaining the results through habit and behaviour change communication. The role of Swachhagrahis and especially Women Swachhagrahis has been pivotal in this mission. They were seen not only as policy implementers but as agents of changes bringing about grassroots level transformation through communication and engagement at the community level. The paper studies the role of women swachhagrahis in transforming the field of sanitation and their role in empowering women through sanitation.

Keywords

Sanitation, Swachh Bharat Mission- Gramin, SBM-G, Swachhagrahis, Women Empowerment.

Introduction

One of the main challenges of sustainable development and worldwide public health is guaranteeing access to safe water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH). For India, this problem has always been enormous, involving not just a lack of infrastructure but also a serious social issue with strong gendered ramifications (Mehta *et al.* 2019). Before the Swachh Bharat Mission (SBM) was introduced in 2014, there was a serious threat to public health, environmental integrity, and human dignity due to the pervasive open defecation. However, a close examination shows that this crisis's burdens were never shared equally (Behera *et al.* 2021). Women and girls were disproportionately affected, and they still are, with particular and severe effects on their socioeconomic well-being, safety, and health (Truelove, Y., and O'Reilly, K. 2020). With women at the forefront of this change, this part lays out the fundamental background of India's sanitation crisis and makes the case that its gendered nature required a paradigm shift in policy, one that went beyond building toilets to community mobilisation (Prakash *et al.* 2022) (Jain *et al.* 2020).

Objective of study

This research paper aims to study role of Women Swachhagrahis in the implementation of Swachh Bharat Mission - Gramin and Women Empowerment in context of Sanitation.

Review of Literature

India had one of the biggest sanitation problems in the world before 2014. Due to a lack of access to basic lavatory facilities, an estimated 568 million people—nearly half of the country's population—practiced open defecation in 2015. With India alone responsible for 90% of all open defecation in South Asia and half of the 1.2 billion people without access to toilets worldwide, this statistic was startling in a global context. The results of this pervasive behaviour were disastrous. Every day, tonnes of untreated human waste were released into the environment, causing soil and water supplies to become widely contaminated by microorganisms (Mukherjee *et al.* 2019).

Nearly 100,000 children under the age of five die from diarrhoeal illnesses each year as a result of this environmental deterioration, which fed a vicious cycle of disease. The economic impact was as high, with poor sanitation resulting in higher medical expenses, lost productivity from illness, and a lower standard of

living that exacerbated poverty throughout generations. The problem was most severe in crowded urban slums and informal settlements, where it was very challenging to provide household-level sanitary facilities due to space constraints and unstable tenure (Kanungo *et al.* 2021). The provision of sustainable WASH services was further complicated by the exacerbation of water scarcity brought on by elements including climate change, fast population increase, and declining groundwater tables. Government-led sanitation programs have existed since 1986, but progress has been sluggish and generally ineffectual, lacking the public support or behavioural changes required to make a significant difference. A national-level intervention of previously unheard-of scope and ambition was made possible by this context of on-going failure and growing environmental and public health emergencies (Morse *et al.* 2020).

In the history of Indian sanitation policy, the October 2, 2014, inauguration of the Swachh Bharat Mission (SBM) marked a turning point. It was intended to be a radical shift in scope and fundamental ideas rather than a gradual improvement on earlier initiatives (Novotný *et al.* 2024). The designers of the mission understood that the Central Rural Sanitation Program (CRSP) and the Total Sanitation Campaign (TSC) had failed because of their primarily supply-driven, subsidy-focused strategy, which led to the construction of millions of toilets that were frequently left unusable or torn apart. The Swachhagrahi, a new type of frontline worker, emerged as the main force behind change since the SBM was developed as a time-bound, mission-mode project that put behaviour modification at the centre of its strategy (Sarkar, S. K. and Bharat, G. K. 2021).

The SBM was established with the specific and audacious objective of making India Open Defecation Free (ODF) by October 2, 2019, which is Mahatma Gandhi's 150th birthday. This goal involved radically changing long-standing social norms and practices in addition to attaining universal sanitation coverage (Narayan *et al.* 2021). The expedition was carried out as a National Jan Andolan (people's movement) and was in line with Sustainable Development Goal 6 of the UN, which demands that everyone have access to water and sanitation. The SBM's transition from a supply-driven to a demand-driven paradigm was its key differentiator. The mission placed more emphasis on creating real demand for sanitation in communities than it did on offering financial incentives for the construction of toilets (Exum *et al.* 2020). The fundamental idea was that people would only construct, use, and maintain toilets if they were persuaded that open defecation needed to be stopped. This demonstrated a deep comprehension that sanitation is a problem that is as much sociological as it is infrastructural.

Main Text

Who are the Swachhagrahis?

Swachhagrahis form the institutional core of the Swachh Bharat Mission's approach to not only build toilet infrastructure but also bring about behavioural change by communication. They are part of human resource essential to convert a national policy goal into a social movement at the village level. A swachhagrahi can be anyone, Asha worker, Anganwadi worker, members of Panchayati Raj Institutes, any youth or any member of the local community. The word swachhagrahi is symbolic of the ideal of Swachhta and Satyagraha of Mahatma Gandhi. They are volunteers taking up the cause of sanitation and devoting their time and energy to bring about social change through participation and communication. They are ideally called the foot soldiers and ambassadors of Swachh Bharat Mission- Gramin in their region. Their initiatives and engagement with the community is essential in both pre- ODF and post- ODF phases. The Swachh Bharat Mission- Gramin, Swachhagrahis Guidelines provide a detailed description about the role of swachhagrahis, their training and providing them with appropriate financial incentives according to various activities carried out by them.

According to the Swachh Bharat Mission principles, inclusion of women swachhagrahis in the sanitation drive is a thought after decision based on a thorough understanding of dynamics and how things work in the community and at village level, rather than just being a token gesture towards gender inclusion. There are a number of significant reasons as to why women are better at implementing WASH initiatives locally, according to academic research and policy experience. First of all, women and girls are usually the worst affected by lack of proper sanitation facilities, having direct impact on their health, wellbeing and safety. Secondly, women have a strong social connection and integration within their groups and communities. They have widespread social networks and are understood to be reliable and trustworthy as compared to others when it comes to being information sources about cleanliness and health issues. Because of this, women are able to have discussions with other women about sensitive and intimate topics and issues such as defecation, menstruation, pregnancy etc.

which would be quite difficult to have with or culturally unacceptable with male employees. Thirdly, there is growing evidence that shows more equitable and sustainable results are seen from women's leadership and participation in WASH (water, sanitation and hygiene) initiatives.

Fourthly, participation and involvement of women has been seen to be associated with better financial management, service delivery, dispute resolution and community trust and participation. Lastly, it is seen that women are main managers providing for water and hygiene needs of the family and lack of these have bearing on their life and wellbeing of the family. Women residing in areas with improper sanitation and hygiene facilities offer first hand insights that improve the implementation and outcome of policies as lack of sanitation becomes their lived experience.

India's approach to sanitation has been completely transformed by the Swachh Bharat Mission's- Gramin creative use of a women-led cadre of Swachhagrahis. Large-scale community mobilisation led by local women leaders has proven to be capable of producing profound changes that have surpassed decades of top-down, infrastructure-focused initiatives. Apart from being face of sanitation drive and the force behind change at the grassroots level, these women have made new identities for themselves as entrepreneurs, leaders, and agents of women empowerment.

Role of Swachhagrahis

Figure 1:- Role of Swachhagrahis

The role and responsibility of swachhagrahis as described in the mission guidelines are spread across three heads namely, planning, implementation and sustainability. Planning phase include the pre implementation activities and initiatives that include community engagement, preparing plan for implementation, knowing sanitation status of households in the region, creating awareness and working to generate demand for toilet construction. Implementation phase include actual toilet construction phase, this include ensuring good quality toilets are constructed, appropriate toilet technology is used, training of masons ,etc. this phase also includes that toilets are not only constructed but also used, ensure habit and behaviour change, meetings with 'nigrani samitis', conducting 'prabhat pheris' and 'ratri chaupals'. Sustainability role include the post toilet construction phase where the main responsibility is to ensure toilet usage, ODF status sustainability, geo-tagging of toilets and conducting of ODF verifications.

Methodology

The study was undertaken to assess the Role of Women Swachhagrahis in the implementation of Swachh Bharat Mission - Gramin. The collection of primary data was done with the help of a structured interview schedule that gathered the views of the women participants in the 4 Panchayat Samitis of the Ajmer District of Rajasthan. The data was collected from 240 participants for the study using a convenience sampling method. The data was then arranged and tabulated. The data was further statistically studied, analysed and presented in the form of tables and charts.

Analysis

Analysis and Interpretation

The results and analysis about the study “ The Role of Women Swachhagrahis in Sanitation Revolution and Women Empowerment: An Empirical Study of Ajmer District of Rajasthan” are discussed below

Table 1:- Types of activities carried out by the Frontline Women Workers in relation to SBM-G

S.No.	Type of activities	Total (%)
1	Personal interaction	90.00
2	Street play/ rally	57.50
3	Games/competition	32.08
4	Posters/ wall painting/ banners	49.58
5	Groups/organizations formed	45.42
6	Fair/ meetings	43.33
7	Other	1.25

Figure 2:- Types of activities carried out by the Frontline Women Workers in relation to SBM-G

The above table 1 and figure 1 show the various activities and initiatives carried out by women employees, including Mahila Sarpanch/Pradhan, ASHA, and Anganwadi workers, to further the objectives of the Swachh Bharat Mission-Gramin (SBM-G) in the four Panchayat Samitis namely Ajmer Rural, Pisangan, Silora, and Srinagar of the Ajmer District of Rajasthan. 90% of the respondents reported engagement through one-on-one interaction, underlining the importance and effectiveness of personal interaction in bringing about change in behavioural attitudes.

Other initiatives involving visual medium and interactive approach includes street plays/rallies (57.50%) and posters/ wall paintings (49.58%). Games and contests (32.08%) and fairs/meetings (43.33%) strengthened behavioural reinforcement by incorporating a community-level engagement especially for women and children. Use of groups or organisations (45.42%) as an approach to bring change and sustain the change is significance as it shows institutionalisation of sanitation goals, which is paramount to sustain the outcomes.

Table 2:- The Role and Cooperation of the Frontline Women Workers being helpful in Women Empowerment

S.No.	Responses	Total (%)
1	Yes	69.17
2	Partial	21.25
3	No	3.33
4	*NA	6.25

*NA- no response

The overwhelming majority (69.17%) gave a positive affirmation, depicting that the activities and initiatives carried out by these women workers' have gone beyond than just supporting the goal of toilet construction of Swachh Bharat Mission - Gramin. They have had a significant role in not only promoting sanitation but also in impacting women's self-esteem, agency, and participation in the community. This illustrates how women-led sanitation projects can serve as springboards for more extensive gender empowerment. By seeing contextual barriers through the "eyes" of those who encounter WASH issues—including their potential, opinions, and needs in the process of problem-solving—participatory techniques might assist in addressing these sometimes-disregarded obstacles (Bisung et al. 2015; Arimoro & Musa 2020). Being included in the decision-making process encourages acceptance, and people are more likely to be committed to implementing solutions that result in sustainable outcomes (Crosby et al. 2020; O'Donovan et al. 2020). Additionally, by addressing local WASH challenges early on, funding for impractical solutions is avoided while taking into account the diversity of local communities' practices, cultures, and means of subsistence. It is essential to foster problem-solving abilities, creativity, and innovation in communities by facilitating the active involvement of community members in problem-solving. This allows the benefits of initiatives to extend beyond their tangible results (Banana et al. 2015; Hetherington et al. 2017).

Furthermore, 21.25% of respondents acknowledged partial contribution, underlining that the roles of these Swachhagrahis are notable and valuable, but there still may be certain limitations. Only 3.33% of the respondents disagreed, and 6.25% of respondents marked a no response to the question, which could indicate that women participants of the survey may not have had clarity about concepts like empowerment.

Overall, the study highlights the significant impact that these Women Swachhagrahis under SBM-G have had in promoting not only better sanitary facilities but also on the dignity, self-esteem and agency of women. To enhance their involvement in women's empowerment and sustainable rural development, these women frontline workers need proper training, resources, recognition and chances to lead.

Table 3:- Assistance provided by Frontline Women Workers in context of Swachh Bharat Mission - Gramin

S.No.	Assistance	Total (%)
1	Swachh Bharat Mission- Gramin Information and Awareness	
	Yes	100
2	Motivation/Awareness for freedom from open defecation	
	No	0.42
	Yes	99.58
3	Motivation/Support for the construction of toilets under – SBM-G	
	*NA	0.83
	No	0.83
	Yes	98.33
4	Listening and understanding problems	
	*NA	0.83
	No	0.83
	Yes	98.33

*NA - no response

Table -3 shows the kind of support that women grassroots actors, such as Mahila Sarpanch/Pradhan, Anganwadi workers, and ASHA workers, have provided to the Swachh Bharat Mission-Gramin (SBM-G) goals in Ajmer Rural, Pisangan, Silora, and Srinagar. The table shows that these Swachhagrahis have a significant and steady function, particularly in providing emotional support, encouraging community, and information sharing.

A cent percent of women participants of the survey confirmed that they were made aware of the government scheme - SBM-G, highlighting the reach and influence of these women workers in their region. 98% women participants shared that they were encouraged and supported to undertake the construction of toilet under Swachh Bharat Mission- Gramin and 99% of women participants expressed

that they were encouraged to give up open defecation making them aware about the ill effects of open defecation that affect not only health and environment but also compromises with their bodily safety and dignity.

Another notable data point has been found through this study that shows that 98% of women participants of the study reported to having had the space to vent out their problems as provided by these women Swachhagrahis. This indicates that the women felt heard and attended to their problems, this is crucial in bringing out change and participation in the society. Hygiene, sanitation and health initiatives in the future must work in the direction of capacity building for these women workers in order to recognise and support their role in promoting public health.

Participation and community engagement were linked to increased adoption of co-developed interventions in the areas of sanitation and hygiene. Specifically, community sanitation participation in Tanzania revealed that 81% of participating families used pit latrines, up from 33% at baseline (Kema et al. 2012). Community engagement resulted in shared ownership, better outcomes, and more relevant insights in addition to risk mitigation and problem short-circuiting in another hygiene-related project in Sierra Leone (Crosby et al. 2020). The community-led sanitation approach, which focused on peer pressure and social motivation rather than financial support, decreased under-5 mortality and boosted positive sanitation practices in a randomised experiment conducted in Mali (Hyun et al. 2019).

Conclusion

In India, the Swachh Bharat Mission-Gramin (SBM-G) has been monumental in making a paradigm shift in sanitation by focussing on behaviour change communication and community mobilisation rather than just infrastructure building. Mahila Sarpanchs, ASHAs, AWWs are among the women frontline workers who have played a crucial part in this revolution in the field of hygiene and sanitation. It is clear from the study that these women swachhagrahis have been the driving forces behind a social change rather than just being the medium of implementing government policies. With over 98% of responders receiving encouragement and support for toilet construction, and 100% of respondents obtaining information regarding SBM-G, this near universal reach signifies their influence and efficiency in communicating about change and development. This ability to communicate to bring about long-lasting behavioural change is shown by their use of a variety of engagement tools such as visual media, community activities, and personal contact among others. More importantly, this highlights how these engagements have evolved into a tool for women empowerment that goes beyond simple sanitation. The substantial socio-cultural influence is highlighted by the fact that 69.17% of respondents agreed that their roles directly aided in women empowerment. By assuming leadership roles, promoting community discourse, and addressing public health issues, these women have not only improved their personal autonomy, self-worth, and standing in their communities, but have also simultaneously shown how participation of women in social change policies and initiatives transform them from change recipients into change agents, making the phrase - 'transformation for women, by women' a reality.

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